

cataracts 13 is a plunger 8, pivotally connected to a lever system 7 picking mechanism and enters during braking into the cylinder. Amount of braking of oil cataracts is changed by the adjusting needle 14.

Full period of work of picking mechanism consists of four separate processes: charging the torsion rod; outputting of mechanism from a dead Charging the torsion rod; discharge (unwinding) of the torsion rod and acceleration of projectile; braking of mechanism.

III. DYNAMIC MODEL OF PICKING MECHANISM

For modeling the movement of picking mechanism during its discharge (See Fig.2), we represent it as an equivalent scheme [1]-[4], shown in Fig. 3. Scheme contains the torsion rod and a movable pipe. Fixed pipe is presented as anchorage end torsion.

Fig. 2 Scheme of picking mechanism

Moments of inertia of the picking mechanism presented in the form of discs 1 and 2 with the reduced moment of inertia $J_1 = J_1(\varphi), J_2 = J_2(\varphi_2)$. By disc 2 is applied reduced torque resistance by an oil plunger $M_C(\varphi_2)$.

Fig. 3 Equivalent scheme of picking mechanism

For the dynamic analysis of the picking mechanism are using software system SimulationX.

SimulationX is a simulation software for physical system simulation, developed and sold commercially by ITI GmbH, based in Dresden, Germany [5]. Scientists and engineers in industry and education use the tool for the design, analysis and virtual testing of complex mechatronics systems, as the software models the interaction of components from a multitude of domains including their mutual interaction and feedback on one platform. ITI launched SimulationX, the

successor of ITI-SIM, in 2000 in response to rising demand for system simulation.

Fig.4 shows the dynamic model of the picking mechanism of Sulzer projectile loom for a period of discharge in SimulationX,

Fig. 4 Dynamic model of the picking mechanism of Sulzer projectile loom

The calculation was made for picking mechanism with torsion rod in diameter 15 mm and twisted by 31 degrees. Torsion stiffness is 590 Nm/rad , a movable pipe stiffness is 80911 Nm/rad .

Diagrams of reduced moments inertia

$J_1 = J_1(\varphi), J_2 = J_2(\varphi_2)$ [6], [7] are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 respectively. Reduced moment of force of resistance from the oil plunger $M_C(\varphi_2)$ [7] is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 5 Reduced moment inertia $J_1 = J_1(\varphi)$

Fig. 6 Reduced moment inertia $J_2 = J_2(\varphi_2)$

Fig. 8 Angular displacement of lever of picking mechanism during its discharge

Fig. 7 Reduced moment of force of resistance from the oil plunger $M_C = M_C(\varphi_2)$

Fig. 9 Angular velocity of lever of picking mechanism during its discharge

IV. RESULTS OF MODELING

We obtained the law of motion of lever of picking mechanism during its discharge. Fig. 8 shows a diagram of angular displacement of lever of picking mechanism during its discharge. Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 show diagram of the angular velocity and acceleration of lever of picking mechanism during its discharge.

Fig. 10 Angular acceleration of lever of the picking mechanism during its discharge

Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 show a diagram of angular displacement and angular velocity of a movable pipe of picking mechanism during its discharge.

Fig. 11 Angular displacement of a movable pipe

Fig. 14 Change of potential energy of a movable pipe

Fig. 12 Angular velocity of a movable pipe

Fig. 15 Change of spring torque of torsion rod

Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 shows a diagram of change of potential energy of torsion rod and a movable pipe of picking mechanism during its discharge. Fig. 15 shows a diagram of change of spring torque of torsion rod.

Table I shows the natural frequencies and modes of the picking mechanism. In Fig. 16 shows a diagram of Campbell.

TABLE I
 NATURAL FREQUENCIES AND MODES\NATURAL FREQUENCIES

No.	Value	f[Hz] undamped	f[Hz] undamped	D[-]	Time constant [s]
f1	-19.663± 312.38i	49.816	49.717	0.062822	0.-50856
T1	-3388.3				0.00029514
T2	-17712				5.6459E-005

Fig. 13 Change of potential energy of torsion rod

Fig. 16 Diagram of Campbell

V. CONCLUSION

As shown in Fig. 6 maximum angular velocity of lever of picking mechanism is $\omega = 123.7 \text{ rad} / c$ at $t = 0.006 c$. Projectile of weft starts flying at a speed $V = 22.89 \text{ m} / c$ at the time $t = 0.006 c$, in good agreement with experimental results shown are in [7].

Construction of dynamic model the picking mechanism of Sulzer projectile loom on software complex SimulationX can make calculations for different thickness of torsion rods taking into account the backlashes in the connections, the dissipative forces and resistance forces.

The necessary results can be obtained in a graphical form and carry out automatically analyze the natural frequencies and mode shapes.

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